

Thermal Behaviour of Metal Biguanides and their Iodine Adducts

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1 : 1 charge transfer adducts of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} biguanides with I_2 have been prepared. Thermal characteristics of metal biguanides, substituted metal biguanides and their charge transfer adducts have been studied. The general features of the thermoanalytical traces are almost same except in case of iodine adducts. The evolution of iodine from the iodine adduct at appreciably lower temperature than the usual iodine compounds confirms the formation of charge transfer complexes of iodine with the metal biguanide.

The concept of aromaticity in metal chelates is a controversial phenomenon though the charge transfer (CT) complexes of metal chelates with different electron acceptors are being established through experimental observations. From uv absorption spectra and approximate MO calculations, Sen¹ proposed a delocalisation of π -electrons over the entire ring of the metal chelate which was supported by nmr studies², XPS³ studies and through several electrophilic substitution reactions on various metal biguanides⁴⁻⁶. It is understood that the presence of a ring current in metal chelates should favour charge transfer interactions with π -acceptors. From spectrophotometric studies Singh and Sahay⁷ concluded that the metal acetyl acetonates have some aromatic character which can favour electrophilic substitution reactions. They even prepared 1:1 CT complexes of this chelate with I_2 in solution⁷. In an earlier communication⁸, Bera *et al.*⁸ reported the formation of CT complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} biguanides with two well-known acceptors, e.g. I_2 and tetracyanoquinodimethane (TCNQ) and tried to establish the idea of CT complex formation spectrophotometrically and kinetically considering the interaction of the t_{2g} orbitals of metals with ligand π -orbitals. Iodine adducts were characterised both in solid and solution states. The appearance of a broad band at 355 nm and shifting of ir frequencies supported the formation of donor-acceptor associates.

It was considered worthwhile to investigate the thermal behaviour of these type of biguanides and its metal complexes as well as the CT compound of these complexes. It was expected that the thermal effect on such complexes would give rise to many interesting phenomena such as, phase transition, bridge formation etc. In the literature, this type of observation is not well mentioned. Hence, in this communication, we are trying to explain the thermal effect of biguanides, substituted biguanides and CT complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} biguanides with I_2 .

Results and Discussion

The results of the elemental analysis and the ir data are summed up in Table 1. The TG traces of the samples are presented in Figs. 1 and 2. The general features of the thermoanalytical traces are almost same except some differen-

ces in particular cases which are taken up individually in the course of our discussion for critical examination.

The TG and the DTA curve of $\text{Cu}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A) are shown in Figs. 1(a) and 3(a) respectively. The probable mechanisms of the thermal changes are presented in the Scheme 1. Several distinct transformation steps are observed in the DTA. On the basis of physicochemical properties of different products obtained after different isothermal steps, the following general mechanism has been suggested.

Scheme 1

The first dehydration step is an endothermic process. The ir spectrum of (B) shows the absence of $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ peak ($\sim 1690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which was present in (A) (Table 1). Compound (B) can be converted to (A) in presence of moisture.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Analysis (%) . Found/(Calcd.)				$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	δ_{NH}	δ_{NH_2}	$\nu_{\text{N-C-N}}$	ν_{NH_2} ν_{NH}	ν_{OH}
	Cu/Ni	N	Cl	I						
$\text{Cu}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	16.95	37.30	19.06	—	1 250	1 430	1 550	1 670	3 220	3 360
	(17.14)	(37.78)	(19.16)		1 280		1 610	1 690	3 280	3 450
$\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	14.34	31.92	16.56	—	1 270	1 410	1 500	1 660	3 240	3 320
	(14.75)	(32.52)	(16.49)		1 320	1 450	1 530			
$\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	13.65	29.12	14.67	—	1 240	1 420	1 520	1 640	3 280	
	(13.29)	(29.32)	(14.87)		1 350	1 480	1 550	1 670		
$\text{Cu}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2$	12.50	28.40	14.09	25.06	1 260	1 430	1 540	1 680	3 280	3 340
	(12.76)	(28.14)	(14.27)	(25.50)			1 610			3 450
$\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2$	10.35	23.30	11.61	19.30	1 250	1 420	1 520	1 660		3 400
	(10.50)	(23.16)	(11.74)	(21.00)	1 350	1 480	1 610			
$\text{Ni}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	15.85	38.00	19.20	—	1 300	1 450	1 550	1 640		3 350
	(16.05)	(38.28)	(19.41)		1 320		1 600	1 680		3 450
$\text{Ni}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	12.30	29.95	15.50	—	1 354	1 493	1 630	1 675		3 366
	(12.90)	(30.78)	(15.61)							
$\text{Ni}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2$	12.67	29.40	14.31	25.60	1 300	1 450	1 530	1 690		3 350
	(11.91)	(28.41)	(14.41)	(25.77)			1 550			3 435
							1 610			

In the next step, the liberated gas was confirmed to be NH_3 chemically and estimated by absorption in H_2SO_4 . This and the mass loss during this transformation indicate the loss of two molecules of ammonia per molecule of (A). The ir spectrum of (C) shows decrease in intensity of δ_{NH_2} ($1\ 610$ – $1\ 630\ \text{cm}^{-1}$). This brownish product (C) appears to be polymeric and sparingly soluble in water from which the Cl^- ion can be precipitated by AgNO_3 . The chemical analysis and the properties of this residue support the suggested structure (C). The next decomposition steps are not easy to distinguish due to the polymeric nature of the product (C) as well as the simultaneous formation of more than one reaction. The HCl evolved in the next step was estimated by absorption in standard NaOH . This compound (D) does not contain any Cl^- and is highly insoluble in water and methanol. The ir spectrum of (D) does not show the band due to δ_{NH_2} which is present in (C).

The last step is exothermic which may be due to the loss of HCN from the molecule and the ir spectrum of this residue shows a peak at $\sim 1\ 350\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$. It is highly insoluble in water and methanol and decomposed by boiling acid explosively at $\sim 480^\circ$. All these suggest the presence of N-N in this compound and hence the structure (E) has been suggested for it. The residue left after exothermic decomposition at $\sim 480^\circ$ was CuCl_2 and some other products.

The thermal behaviour of $\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is slightly different from the previous one (Fig. 1b). The compound is dehydrated endothermally at 150° in a single step. The dehydration temperature is higher in this case relative

to the previous one, indicating the presence of stronger H-bonding. The next endothermic steps occur at ~ 216 and 228° with loss of 2 moles of NH_4Cl per molecule of the compound. The presence of NH_4Cl in the outgoing gases was detected by the presence of solid deposit in the cooler part of the heating tube and the amount was estimated as stated earlier. The loss of NH_4Cl at appreciably lower temperature relative to previous one suggests the lower

Fig. 1 TG traces of (a) $\text{Cu}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (b) $\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (c) $\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

thermal stability of the compound. The residue thus obtained was insoluble in water and methanol and could not be converted to the original compound by any means. They appeared to be polymeric in nature and it decomposed finally at 525° .

The thermal pattern of $\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is almost identical to that of the normal biguanide. Here the dehydration takes place at 112 and 132° in two steps and the deamination temperature is also comparable to the Cu-n-biguanide compound. The decomposition part is almost similar to the previously stated thermograms.

The DTA curves of Cu-n-biguanide and the iodine adduct of this complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{I}_2]$ are compared in the Fig. 3. The first endothermic step for the adduct starts at reasonably higher temperature than the original biguanide (118° for biguanide while in case of the adduct endothermic peak started at 132°). The mass-loss in case of iodine adduct indicates the evolution of two molecules of H_2O and half a molecule of I_2 at the first two steps up to 170°. This can be corroborated if iodine is being considered as in association with the complex forming a weak bond (with the help of delocalisation of the electron). The presence of iodine makes the water association stronger due to which water elimination is also taking place at higher temperature. The next deamination step at 244° takes place endothermally with a very sharp peak. After this temperature a continuous weight-loss up to 436° is observed and a definite pattern of decomposition steps is not distinguishably prominent. In the last step, an exothermic change might have taken into consideration all sorts of decomposition steps and produced the final residue.

Fig 2 TG traces of (a) $\text{Ni}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (b) $\text{Ni}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl} \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (c) $\text{Ni}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2$

The TG pattern of the iodine adduct of the diethyl substituted biguanide $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2]$ is also similar to that of the previous adduct, only the range of temperature in some steps is slightly varying. In the first step (120–150°) evolution of water and iodine occurs simultaneously. The elimination of I_2 at a lower temperature than the previous adduct indicates the weaker association of the iodine with the complex. The next deamination step evolving (Et_2NH) is completed at 290°. The last exothermic step occurs with a great weight loss.

The thermogram of $\text{Ni}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is shown in Fig. 2(a) and the probable mechanism based on the experimental observations for the thermal decomposition is given in

Scheme 2. This complex loses water molecules endothermally in the range 100–125°. In the next step deamination takes place in the range of 300–325° in which two molecules of NH_3 per one molecule are lost as evidenced by absorption in H_2SO_4 as well as the mass-loss during the process. The residue thus obtained (C) is slightly water-soluble and the presence of Cl^- was detected by AgNO_3 method. The next slightly exothermic step starts immediately at 330° and the process is accompanied by small exothermic change without any appreciable mass loss. During this process the orange-yellow colour of the compound changes completely to green on isothermal heating at $\sim 340^\circ$ for an appreciable long time (~ 2 h). This compound (D) is paramagnetic in nature. The next step is very indistinct forming (E) and it is found that heating under dry nitrogen the compound (E) decomposes at 570° to give the residue as NiCl_2 with some other products.

The thermograms of $\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are very much comparable to the previous one. For the diethyl substituted complex the dehydration takes place at 100° with a very low intensity endothermic peak (Fig. 2b). The lower number of lattice water molecules relative to the other compounds may be due to the presence of ethyl groups which decrease the number of H-atoms required for H-bonding and at the same

Scheme 2

time increase the steric factors. The next step may be due to the liberation of Et_2NH which is completed at 310° . The process is a mixture of endo- and exothermic steps and probably $>\text{CNEt}_2$ group is weaker relative to $>\text{CNH}_2$ group resulting in the elimination of Et_2NH at lower temperature compared to that in case of biguanide complex. The residue obtained after diethylamination is identical to (C) in physicochemical properties, its spectra and in all further degradation processes. Hence it is suggested that the mechanism of all the next thermal processes are similar to the previous one. The TG trace of the iodine adduct of nickel biguanide [$\text{Ni}(\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2$] is shown in Fig. 2(c). The thermogram shows that elimination of water and iodine takes place in a single step. The other decomposition steps are almost similar to that of the nickel biguanide complex.

In all the iodine adduct of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} biguanides, the elimination of iodine takes place at appreciably lower temperatures than the usual iodide compounds and confirms the formation of charge transfer complexes of iodine with the metal biguanides where we suggest a weak association of iodine molecule with the delocalised π -electrons present over the entire ring of the metal chelates.

Experimental

The bis(ligand) complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were prepared in the pure form by the reported method⁹ (where ligand = n-biguanide/alkyl substituted biguanides). All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Methanol and dimethylformamide were of spectroscopic grade. Specially prepared conductivity water was used for preparing solutions.

Preparation of the adducts : Iodine and bis(ligand)-metal chlorides were dissolved in minimum volume of methanol in a 1 : 1 molar ratio. The violet colour of the Cu^{II} complex changed instantly to brown. On evaporating the solution slowly at room temperature, the needle-shaped reddish brown crystals of the Cu^{II} adduct separated out. The Ni^{II} adduct was obtained as light brown flakes from

their methanolic solution in the same manner. The adducts were crystallised from dimethyl sulphoxide and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 . Metal, iodine, nitrogen and chlorine contents in the solid products were estimated by standard analytical procedures and compared to the calculated stoichiometry. Though $\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{bg})_2\text{Cl}_2\text{-I}_2$ adduct was isolated in the solid state, it was not very stable over time (~15 days). The other Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} bis-substituted-biguanide complexes reacted with methanolic iodine solution with an instantaneous change of colour from violet/orange to brown/brick-red, but no solid compound could be isolated.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with Perkin-Elmer 298B spectrophotometer in air at ambient temperature. The spectra were taken for metal biguanide chlorides and the corresponding iodine adducts in solid. DTA and TG analyses were carried out on a Shimadzu DT-40 thermal analyzer unit in nitrogen medium at a heating rate of 15°min^{-1} .

Detection of products during thermal decomposition :

After obtaining the derivatograph of any particular compound, the compound was heated isothermally at the mean temperature of inception and final temperature of any particular reaction in a slow current of nitrogen dried by passing through magnesium perchlorate. The heating was continued till the particular reaction was over. The water vapour formed during the process was detected by passing through anhydrous CuSO_4 and estimated through absorption by magnesium perchlorate. NH_3 formed during reaction was estimated by absorbing it in 0.1 N H_2SO_4 and back-titrating the excess acid with a standard alkali solution using methyl orange as indicator. In case of evolution of HCl or HCN, the gas mixture was passed through NaOH solution and HCl was estimated by AgCl method while HCN was detected by converting it to $\text{KFe}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$. The NH_4Cl formed was detected in the solid deposit obtained in the cooler parts of the heating tube and NH_3 was released by boiling the solution with concentrated NaOH and estimated by passing the gas through 0.1 N H_2SO_4 . The chloride was estimated by AgNO_3 method.

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